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FACTORS INFLUENCING THE FORMATION OF THE PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION SYSTEM IN EDUCATION IN UKRAINE

The article has examined the external and internal factors influencing the formation of the system of public administration in education in Ukraine, and their classification is determined, and features are highlighted.

Key words: *public administration in education, educational policy, management system, factors of influence, classification.*

В статті досліджено зовнішні та внутрішні чинники, що впливають на формування системи публічного управління освітою в Україні, визначено та запропоновано їх класифікацію, виділені особливості.

Ключові слова: *публічне управління освітою, освітня політика, система управління, чинники впливу, класифікація.*

Problem setting. As a social and cultural phenomenon, education is an important factor in the evolutionary development of mankind. In a rapidly changing world, it becomes a productive force and guarantor of the national security of the

state, as the socio-economic development of society is increasingly dependent on the knowledge and education of every citizen [0, p. 13].

Education functions within the appropriate external environment, which is in constant interaction. Formation of the national system of public administration in education, as well as changes in the educational system of Ukraine, are taking place simultaneously with the development of the global civilization under the influence of a number of factors. According to the dictionary of the Ukrainian language, the factor is a condition, a driving force, the cause of any process that determines its character or one of its main features. This concept is derived from the notion of "do", "act", "carry out a certain act", that is, "what is doing, exercising influence, acting" [10]. Consequently, the factors influencing the formation of the national system of public administration in education are the driving forces, causes and conditions of the development of processes taking place in global education and in its management.

Recent research and publications analysis. In modern management theory, research is conducted on factors influencing efficiency, methods, style, system, and organizational structure of management; on foreign economic, internal economic, innovative, and other activities of the state. The influence of external and internal factors on the efficiency of management is also studied. Scientists develop and offer their system (group) of factors, proving the significance of each factor that influences the processes in a certain area of activity, including education. In particular, the researchers investigate the factors influencing the formation, implementation and state of educational policy, the development and functioning of the educational sector, the management of the education system, etc. Outside Ukrainian researchers' attention remains the study of factors which influence the formation of the national system of education management, which led to the choice of the research topic.

Paper objective. The purpose of the article is to carry out an analysis of scientific literature in which the subject of the research is determined; to discover and explore the whole range of factors influencing the formation of the national system of public administration in education, to classify them and determine their specific features.

Paper main body. In research papers devoted to the development of education, scientists point to a variety of factors and usually group them, using a system of distribution in groups according to certain characteristics. In particular, factors are divided: by the nature of action to external and internal; by nature conditions – objective, subjective; by content – political, historical, legal, economic, social, demographic, psychological, technical; by the nature of influence – direct, indirect (mediated); by level of influence – global, national, regional, local, personal; by the result of influence – positive, negative; by coverage – general, special, etc. This classification allows us to streamline the factors and to identify their general patterns and characteristic features inherent in individual types [0, p. 80].

In this study, we are going to identify external and internal factors that influence the formation of the system of public education in Ukraine, which are described in scientific papers of Ukrainian scientists. In this case, external factors will be considered as world-wide conditions influencing the formation of the national system of public administration in education; internal – as conditions inherent in the external environment.

We note that educational policy is a kind of internal policy, its formation depends to a certain extent on international processes, world trends, including the educational field, which are characteristic for most countries and which are not only preserved, but even strengthen more today. Among the educational trends that are most widespread in the world, public administration scientists call the following: expanding education coverage of population; providing long-life education; equal access to quality education; strengthening the state's role in guaranteeing equity of education; effective and efficient use of education expenditures; humanization and democratization of education; updating of content, forms, methods and means of teaching; increase of professional competence of teachers; the formation of state-public administration in education; dissemination of information on the quality of educational services (transparency of educational systems) [0, c. 24]. However, these factors, according to the authors, are caused by trends in global development, such as: accelerating the pace of society development; transition to a post-industrial,

informational society; the emergence and growth of global problems; democratization of society; dynamic economic development, increasing competition; an increase in human capital value.

The main external factors influencing the education system, as K. Nyemets', P. Virchenko, H. Kulyeshova claim, are globalization and internationalization, which are manifested not only in the strengthening of interrelationships and interdependencies of individual economies, but also in the formation of a global educational space. The authors believe that "the processes of internationalization of educational activities affect the academic mobility of students and teachers, the quantitative and qualitative indicators of providing educational services to foreign students and scientific-pedagogical workers, etc. Internationalization in education manifests itself in the establishment and expansion of multilateral ties and contacts between educational institutions of different countries, in increasing the efficiency of academic and research activities (conducting joint international scientific seminars, conferences, research programs and projects, etc.) based on mutually beneficial partnership basis» [0, p. 30-31].

S. Krysyuk also defines globalization as a defining universal principle and a major factor shaping the new relationships between nations and economic systems based on high professionalism, employee competitiveness, and the growing importance of knowledge as an important condition for economic development. In his opinion, the last decades of the XXth and the first decade of the XXIst centuries were marked by major global changes (increasing the importance of knowledge as an important factor of economic growth in the global context, the information and communication revolution, the emergence of the global labor market, socio-political transformations of a global scale) that significantly influenced the role, functions and ways of functioning of education throughout the world, particularly in Ukraine. As to the development of state administration in education S. Krysyuk notes that this process takes place in accordance with development of the society and the state and is influenced by a number of trends and factors of social development. The leading role among them is played by the external environmental processes, such as:

globalization and its challenges; the transition to the information society; democratization; emancipation of people [0].

According to I. Ivanyuk, the decisive factor for Ukraine is the integration of Ukrainian education, especially the higher education, into the European educational space as a direction of cooperation between the country and the EU, which can lead to significant success in all other European integration processes [**Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.**3, p. 153]. This is confirmed by N. Khvorostyana and M. Vyelikzhanina, who note that the global factors associated with the problem of ensuring the quality of education in Ukraine are: the impact of scientific and technological progress on the lives of Ukrainians; the need for appropriate changes in the training of market economy specialists; the state's course to European integration and, consequently, the need to take into account the requirements of the Bologna educational process; the expansion and acquisition of a new quality of democratic processes and the building of a civil society [0, p. 25].

So, summing up scientific researches, one can conclude: firstly, there is no clear list of external factors inherent in the process of forming the national system of education management in Ukraine, since the authors define them differently; secondly, some scientists determine the external factors influencing the formation and development of the educational system, while others determine those that influence the process of formation of the education management system; thirdly, the vast majority of scholars believe that external factors are shaped by the influence of global trends, among the most significant are globalization and internationalization [0, p. 81].

It should be noted that external factors are closely interrelated with internal ones: on the one hand, the management system of education creates the internal environment under the influence and on the basis of external factors, on the other - this system adapts to the external environment with the help of the internal factors, which represent a set of internal variables of the system (goals, tasks, structure, resources, technology, vocational and organizational culture) that directly affect management activities. Thus, internal factors influence the effectiveness of both the

management system itself and the development of the educational sector.

Since the declaration of Ukraine's independence both external and internal factors have been taken into account at the formation of educational policy. Thus, in the course of elaboration and adoption of basic legislative acts and program documents for the development of education the social climate in the society, political, economic and other factors were taken into account according to Ye. Krasnyakov. At the legislative level socio-political and economic factors were considered and state guarantees for pedagogical and scientific and pedagogical workers were secured, in particular, the provision of proper working conditions, private life, rest, medical care, promotion, decent salaries. In the 90's of the XXth century an uncontrolled process of closing down educational institutions was launched in Ukraine, because of, first of all, the demographic factor and under the slogan of optimization, which led to a reduction of the network of general education institutions, a decrease in the average class fill rate, an increase in the number of small schools, which led to a reduction in didactic quota, etc. [0]. These processes are most acutely felt by the inhabitants of villages. At the same time, executive bodies on the ground, as well as local self-government, continued to comply with the current legislation, the articles of which did not fully reflect the real situation in education and did not solve educational problems.

Environmental issues are still important factors for Ukraine, among which the Chernobyl catastrophe occupies the most important place. Today the state continues to allocate a large share of expenditures on social protection of the citizens who suffered from this disaster.

One can consider another group of factors also relevant for modern Ukraine, where a part of the territory is occupied by the Russian Federation, and in another part – there are military actions, among which are: political and legal (forced transformation of educational policy; revision and adoption of a number of regulations concerning the occupied territories) ; organizational (creation of military administrations, review of managerial functions); socio-psychological (creation of conditions for education, organization of psychological support), etc.

As for the system of public administration, the determining factor for improving the efficiency of its management activity is managerial competence – "a set of knowledge and skills necessary for performing specific functions that reflect the main directions, types and forms of management activity, and in general form the basis of the model of official competence" [0, p. 82]. Today, an important component of the professional competence of the manager, which determines the success of management activities, is the ability to establish effective communication, to have communication skills, leadership qualities, ability to perceive, analyze and interpret information, ability to solve conflicts, set clear goals, etc. This is especially needed during the implementation of educational reforms that have been conducted in Ukraine since the 1990s.

It should be noted that the functions of the public administration system reflect the content and nature of managerial influence. One of the main functions is planning, the content of which is setting goals and objectives, determining the ways to achieve the goals needed for this resource and developing relevant plans of activity [0, p. 747]. The importance of this function is emphasized by K. Ewers in his work [0]. The scientist suggests, while planning educational policy, taking into account both the internal aspect of the educational system and external economic and social factors: the prospects for economic development by sectors; demographic forecast; development of human capital for the future; the relationship between the education and the standard of living; educational opportunities (educational institutions, the education coverage of population); demand for educational services; the cost of introducing alternative methods and technologies, etc. Consequently, planning should be long-term and non-alternative. At the same time, it is necessary to consider the social processes taking place in the world, to monitor the needs for labor force and investments in the international labor market.

Conclusions of the research. The analysis of scientific literature made it possible to identify and explore a number of external and internal factors that influence the formation of the system of public administration in education, as well as modern trends, on which the managerial activity of the whole system depends. We

propose to classify the factors of the environment that serves as a source of ensuring the formation of public administration in education, namely:

- factors of the external (international) environment (globalization, internationalization, democratization, integration);
- factors of the internal (national) environment:
 - macro factors (political, legal, economic, social, demographic, scientific, technical, technological, cultural, natural);
 - factors of the meso-environment (market, regional, sectoral, strategic, organizational, resource);
 - factors of the microenvironment (human resources, socio-psychological, motivational, scientific-methodological, informational).

The consideration of these groups of factors in managerial activities, which needs to be adapted to the modern educational trends, gives the opportunity to choose the concept, principles, approaches, methods, etc., which are optimal for administration.

Internal factors that directly influence the formation of the national system of public education management demand further research, and there is also a need to study their peculiarities at each level of the environment.

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